

HTA

Humanities & Technology Association

Call for Submissions

Fall 2017 edition of The Humanities and Technology Review

We are happy to announce the call for submissions for the 2017 edition of *The Humanities and Technology Review*. The *HTR* is a double-blind, peer-reviewed, scholarly journal that explores the impact of technology on human life from a broad range of perspectives. We welcome papers that investigate the cultural interaction of the humanities, science, engineering, and technology.

The theme for this year's journal is, *Morality and Creativity in a Technological Age*.

Possible themes for submissions include the ethics of coding technologies; the ethics of gene technology and human engineering; the use of GMOs and questions of food security, along with papers that address how changes in technology carry implications for social and political thought.

All papers examining vital issue areas at the juncture of technology and society will be considered.

For submission guidelines see: <http://htronline.weebly.com/guidelines-for-authors.html>

Deadline for submissions: June 30th, 2017

Please send submissions and questions to Dr. Sean Erwin at Serwin@barry.edu